

Transforming Physical Training with Real-time Pose Analysis using MoveNet

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Abstract: - The proposed system implementation done using MoveNet technology is used for detecting the key body points for precision post detection in physical training purpose that finds much applications in health, sports and fitness domains. The MoveNet tool is used to detect and deliver accurate real-time assessments of specific exercise modules particularly during activities like push-ups. The model has advantage to empower fitness enthusiasts and sports persons to receive immediate feedback in real time workout sessions at professional level without the physical guidance of an expert trainer. The implementation process includes: accessing live video feed, capturing key body points, processing these points to calculate motion angles, updating the repetition count in real-time, and providing immediate live feedback to users. This advanced solution not only counts push-ups accurately but also guides users to achieve precision in their performance, thereby transforming the way people approach physical training and exercise.

Keywords— MoveNet, TensorFlow

I. INTRODUCTION

MoveNet TensorFlow is a groundbreaking technology that offers real-time tracking of 17 key body points with two variants, "Lightning" and "Thunder." It revolutionizes fitness routines and has applications in healthcare, sports analysis, and entertainment. By tracking body movements in real time, MoveNet supports precision training, reduces the risk of injury, and enhances the exercise experience. It's valuable for live fitness apps, aids in patient recovery, and contributes to motion capture in the entertainment industry. MoveNet's practical use in a push-up counter automates counting while ensuring correct form and minimizing injury risk. This confluence of technology and wellness transforms fitness and well-being approaches.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In this Documentation the authors talk about MoveNet: Ultra-fast and accurate pose detection model [1], they provides insights into the technical aspects of using MoveNet and its applications.

In this paper the author give a fable abstract Human Pose Classification with MoveNet and TensorFlow Lite implementation details and its performance [2]

Pose estimation and classification on edge devices with MoveNet and TensorFlow Lite [4]: This paper discusses using MoveNet for pose estimation and classification on edge devices. It may provide insights into deploying MoveNet for real-world applications with resource constraints.

Next-Generation Pose Detection with MoveNet and TensorFlow.js [5] This paper present MoveNet as a next-generation pose detection model and discusses its architecture. It likely provides insights into MoveNet's approach to accurate human pose detection and guide to its performance along with other pose detection technologies.

III. METHODOLOGY

BASIC TERMINOLOGIES USED:

A. MoveNet:

MoveNet is a specialized model designed for detecting key points on the human body with great speed and accuracy. It has two versions, "Lightning" and "Thunder," each with specific traits. Lightning is faster and suitable for tasks where quick results are needed, while Thunder is slower but offers higher precision.

Fig 1 MoveNet architecture

Fig 2 An example of pose classification using MoveNet.

B. Pose Estimation:

Pose estimation is the process of determining the positions of key body points, such as joints and landmarks, in images or videos. MoveNet excels in pose estimation by identifying 17 key body points, enabling applications like exercise tracking and health monitoring.

Fig 3. Configuration of valid human pose estimation.

Fig.4. Types of human body modelling

C. Real-time Performance:

Real-time performance refers to how quickly a system can process and analyze data. MoveNet is known for its exceptional real-time performance, capable of achieving pose estimation at speeds exceeding 30 frames per second (FPS). This means it can provide immediate feedback, making it suitable for fitness tracking and other time-sensitive applications.

MoveNet is a state-of-the-art pose estimation model designed for real-time performance, particularly on mobile and edge devices. Its key features include:

Real-Time Processing: MoveNet is optimized for real-time inference. It can efficiently estimate human poses in live video streams, making it suitable for applications where low latency is crucial.

Mobile and Edge Devices: MoveNet is specifically tailored for mobile and edge devices, allowing it to run smoothly on modern smartphones and other resource-constrained platforms.

Low Computational Cost: The model is designed to be computationally efficient, ensuring that it doesn't consume excessive processing power, which is essential for real-time applications.

Accuracy: Despite its real-time performance, MoveNet doesn't compromise on accuracy. It can accurately detect 17 keypoints of the human body, making it suitable for various pose estimation tasks.

Joint Angle Analysis: MoveNet can be used for joint angle analysis, making it valuable for applications that require precise joint angle predictions for tasks like shoulder flexion and extension.

DATA COLLECTION

- A. **Data Source:** The study involved collecting live video recordings of individuals performing push-up exercises in real-time.
- B. **Data Preparation:** Video Segmentation: For live videos, real-time segmentation techniques were employed to isolate individual push-up repetitions.
- C. **Data Labeling:** Keypoints representing body landmarks (e.g., wrists, elbows, shoulders) were manually labeled in real-time for each frame within the live video streams.

MODEL TUNING

Pose Detection: The study utilized the MoveNet model for real-time pose detection. This model allows the identification of key body locations, enabling the tracking of movements during live push-ups .

Key Point Detection: The employed MoveNet model was used to detect keypoints for each frame in the live video streams.

Key Point Tracking: Key points, including wrists and shoulders, were tracked in real-time to monitor body movements during live push-ups.

Pose Analysis

Repetition Detection: Push-up repetitions were identified by tracking the upward and downward motion of the body in real-time.

Correctness Evaluation: Real-time correctness evaluation was performed by analyzing the alignment of body keypoints with a correct push-up form during live sessions.

Data Visualization: Real-time data visualization was employed to illustrate the correctness of push-up forms in each repetition and identify any deviations during live sessions and computer vision techniques for live video data. The data collection process, selection of the MoveNet model for real-time pose estimation, and real-time data analysis methods provided valuable insights into push-up performance during live sessions.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

A. Initialization

Initialization: The code initializes the necessary components, including the MoveNet pose detection model and various libraries, to set up real-time pose detection. **Webcam Video Stream:** It captures the user's webcam video stream, a fundamental step for capturing live video data.

B. Identifying Pivot Points

Pose Estimation: Through a continuous loop using the set Timeout() function, the code estimates poses continuously in real-time. **Display:** The draw() function is utilized to display the webcam video feed and overlay keypoints and skeletons based on estimated poses, offering visual feedback and tracking the number of completed push-up exercises.

C. Counting Repetitions and Sets

Monitoring Key Points: Functions like drawKeypoints() and drawSkeleton() are used to monitor key points and draw lines connecting them, enhancing the visualization of pose detection.

Calculating Angles and Positions: Functions such as updateArmAngle(), updateBackAngle(), inUpPosition(), and inDownPosition() are employed to calculate the angles of body parts and determine positions, including monitoring elbow and back angles for pose analysis.

D. User Interaction and Feedback

Live Text Display: The code dynamically updates and displays the number of push-ups completed, providing real-time feedback on the user's progress.

Text-to-Speech Feedback: The code employs text-to-speech functionality to offer live vocal feedback, guiding the user during the exercise, announcing "Up," and counting completed push-ups.

This combined approach ensures that the user receives instant feedback, enhancing their exercise experience and promoting precise push-up performance.

V. RESULTS

Visual insights into the performance of our system during push-up exercises. We present three key images that illustrate different aspects of the user's experience

Push-Up Starting Position:

Fig 5. Push-Up Starting Position

This image represents the initial posture when the user is in the starting position for a push-up exercise.

Posture Error Detection:

Fig 6. Posture Error Detection

In this image, red lines are overlaid on the user's body to indicate posture errors during a push-up. The system highlights areas where the user's posture deviates from the correct form.

Successful Repetition:

Fig 7 Successful Repetition

This image showcases a successful push-up repetition with proper posture. The absence of red lines indicates that the user maintained the correct form.

VI. CONCLUSION

MoveNet presents a compelling case for its superiority over Media Pipe Pose in the domain of pose estimation. This newer model offers a trifecta of advantages – speed, accuracy, and robustness – that collectively make it the preferred choice for a range of applications.

MoveNet's remarkable speed is a standout feature, particularly suited for real-time pose estimation on mobile devices, which is crucial in scenarios requiring instantaneous pose analysis. Its higher accuracy, especially in challenging poses and scenarios with occluded joints, extends its utility to a wider spectrum of applications.

Moreover, MoveNet's robustness to noise, variations in lighting, and image quality positions it as the go-to option for real-world environments where conditions may not always be ideal. The performance benchmarks underscore MoveNet's prowess, with consistent outperformance across multiple categories, while real-world applications like fitness tracking, virtual reality, and augmented reality showcase its practical advantages. In sum, MoveNet emerges as a more potent and versatile pose estimation model, firmly establishing itself as the superior solution in this field when compared to Media Pipe Pose.

Fig 8. PDJ in all actions in the video dataset.

	MediaPipe Pose	OpenPose	PoseNet	MoveNet
Action 1	66.62	39.94	68.47	68.70
Action 2	48.38	5.20	41.20	58.68
Action 3	74.21	52.35	77.55	80.58
Action 4	48.92	21.04	56.69	53.95
Action 5	76.34	45.44	72.34	75.67
Action 6	79.00	54.71	77.49	81.42
Action 7	72.10	44.17	69.72	69.31
Action 8	92.57	72.03	92.06	91.21
Action 9	78.03	35.98	76.45	71.85
Action 10	63.59	14.11	48.66	66.73
Action 11	66.32	17.63	54.89	64.68
Action 12	46.56	23.93	48.97	50.36
Action 13	75.72	52.12	72.99	74.79
Action 14	70.17	41.91	65.82	69.93
Average PDJ (%)	68.47	37.16	65.95	69.85

Fig 9. Overall average of PDJ (%) in each action.

VII. REFERENCES

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